

Thermodynamics of Complex Formation between Neodymium(III) and Carboxymethylthiosuccinic Acid and Equilibrium Study of Mixed Complexes with Simple and Substituted Dicarboxylic Acids

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Complexing of neodymium ion with carboxymethylthiosuccinic and dicarboxylic acids have been studied in aqueous solution potentiometrically and the relevant stability constants have been evaluated using computer technique. Carboxymethylthiosuccinic acid has been shown to form 1 : 2 complexes more readily than other dicarboxylic acids. The thermodynamics of the complex formation have been evaluated by potentiometric equilibrium data and the relationship between the site of coordination, and the thermodynamic quantities has been discussed. The results of mixed complexes are explained in terms of substituent influences upon the chelation of malonic and succinic dianions to Nd^{III}-CMTSA systems and the relationship between stabilization parameter ($\Delta \log K$) and the ligand basicity.

THE pronounced biological activity^{1,2} of the metal complexes of ligands derived from thio acids has led to interest in their coordination chemistry. However, studies made so far deal exclusively with the stereochemistry of transition metal complexes^{3,4} and the coordination behaviour of these ligands with organometallic moieties^{5,6}. Our continuing interest in chelated Cu^{II} and Nd^{III} complexes has led us to suggest the tridentate and bidentate nature of thiodiacetic acid^{7,8} and to study their stereochemistry along with their biological activity.

We report here, in addition to few data for binary complexes already reported⁹ the equilibrium studies on the mixed-ligand complex formation occurring when neodymium(III) is mixed with carboxymethylthiosuccinic and dicarboxylic acids. Special consideration was made for the investigation of the substituent effects as favouring the unsymmetrical rather than the symmetrical dimethyl derivatives¹⁰.

Experimental

The dicarboxylic acids such as succinic, itaconic, chlorosuccinic, methylmalonic, dimethylmalonic, ethylmalonic, diethylmalonic, thiodiacetic and 3,3'-thiodipropionic were of Fluka and AnalaR grade. Carboxymethylthiosuccinic acid (CMTSA) was of AnalaR quality. Neodymium nitrate (AnalaR) was used and its concentration was estimated as Nd₂O₃. All solutions were prepared in conductivity-water (pH=6.8, conductivity=1.6 × 10⁻⁵ Ω⁻¹). The details of other chemicals are described in our earlier reports¹¹⁻¹³.

Neodymium complex formation constants were calculated from potentiometric titration curves of the carboxymethylthiosuccinic and dicarboxylic acids in absence and presence of neodymium. Changes in pH were followed using glass and calomel electrodes, and Elico L1-10 digital pH meter. All investigations were carried out under nitrogen atmosphere at 30° and ionic strength 0.1 mol dm⁻³ (NaClO₄). From the calculation of the formation constants a Fortran computer programme was used for the evaluation of equilibrium constants and the concentrations of the species present in the ternary complex. All computations were made at Tata Institute of Fundamental Research, Bombay.

Results and Discussion

The results of the equilibrium studies are summarized in Table 1 in addition to the few data for binary complexes already reported. In the present work, stability constant values are comparable with those reported in the literature and the values differ at different experimental conditions. The standard deviation of the data for the equilibrium constants of binary and ternary complexes was ±0.05 log units. A representative data, i.e. Nd^{III} carboxymethylthiosuccinic-thiodipropionic acid system explain adequately the precision of the experimental work (Table 2).

We have previously elucidated the binding properties of carboxymethylthiosuccinic acid with lanthanides, particularly neodymium ion, employing the equilibrium constant data, thermodynamic parameters and also the electrostatic and cratic

TABLE 1—PROTON AND NEODYMIUM COMPLEX FORMATION CONSTANTS FOR CARBOXYMETHYLTHIOSUCCINIC ACID (CMTSA) AND DERIVED THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

Constants	Temp. 30°, $\mu = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$			
	$pK/\log K$	ΔG kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
pK_1	2.91 2.80 ^a	16.91 (4)	5.27 (12)	9.2 (4)
pK_2	3.91 3.90 ^a 3.79 ^b	22.69 (3)	3.51 (14)	15.1 (7)
pK_3	5.03 5.05 ^a	29.21 (3)	3.52 (15)	20.3 (9)
$\log K_1^0$	4.10	-23.79	-4.37	+92.9
$\log K_2^0$	3.25	-18.86	-6.13	+82.4

Standard deviation in parentheses.

^aRef. 28, ^bRef. 29, ^cRef. 15.

TABLE 2—EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANT FOR THE NEODYMIUM(III)-CARBOXYMETHYLTHIOSUCCINIC ACID (CMTSA) (Y)-THIODIPROPIONIC ACID (X) SYSTEM

pH	Temp. = 30°, $\mu = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$				
	$[H^+] \times 10^5$	K_{MY}^M	K_{DXY}	K_{MX}^{MX}	K_{MY}^{MY}
4.35	5.372	7.773	1.313	3.673	4.563
4.45	4.267	7.797	1.337	3.697	4.587
4.60	3.020	7.773	1.313	3.673	4.563
4.70	2.399	7.759	1.299	3.659	4.549
4.80	1.905	7.768	1.309	3.669	4.559
4.85	1.698	7.760	1.300	3.660	4.550
4.90	1.513	7.763	1.303	3.663	4.553
4.95	1.349	7.777	1.317	3.677	4.567
Average		7.768	1.307	3.667	4.557

components of these thermodynamic parameters^{14,15}. The formation of Nd^{III}-CMTSA complexes is enthalpically disfavoured but entropically favoured. This indicates that the metal ion is bound to oxygen of the carboxylate groups of carboxymethylthiosuccinic acid. The contribution to the total enthalpy by the carboxylate group in complexation was apparently either very small or probably slightly endothermic, suggesting that no information of the metal ion with sulphur donor atoms is present in neodymium complexes. This explanation of the thermodynamic data is in agreement with that previously suggested^{16,17}, and very recent report^{18,19} for mixed-ligand complexes. The stability constants obtained for methyl and ethyl malonic acids are expected on the basis of nature of substituent in the parent malonic except in dimethylmalonic acid.

To extend the complexity of the system as a means of characterising by electronic and ir spectra as spectroscopic probe have been investigated. It has been observed that there is no interaction between sulphur atom and neodymium ion.

Further, the prepared solid complex is paramagnetic, giving Bohr Magneton values corresponding to one unpaired electrons. These detailed studies will be reported in a forthcoming publication.

The stabilization constant of the complex stability ($\Delta \log K$) is the difference between measured values of stability constants which is defined²⁰ as

$$\Delta \log K = \log K_{MX}^{MX} - \log K_{MY}^{MY} \\ = \log K_{MY}^{MY} - \log K_{MX}^{MX} \quad (1)$$

The disproportionation constant (K_{DXY}) can be given by reaction (2)

The complex stability is a measure of the affinity that secondary acid has bonding to the aquated metal ion and to the complexes Nd^{III}-CMTSA. Since more coordinating sites are available for bonding the first ligand to a metal ion than for the second ligand, $\Delta \log K$ should, in general be negative²¹. In aqueous solution neodymium ion²² is present as $[Nd(H_2O)_6]^{3+}$, $[Nd(H_2O)_8]^{3+}$ and $[Nd(H_2O)_9]^{3+}$. The metal chelate is formed due to the simultaneous replacement of water molecules from the coordination sphere of neodymium ion with the formation of Nd-O bonds. Thus the values of $\Delta \log K$ and K_{DXY} would be -0.6 and 0.6, respectively, values markedly greater than these suggesting the preferential formation of mixed-ligand complexes than binary ones. However, the value of K_{DXY} is clearly dependent on the stabilities of the simple binary bis-complexes.

Table 3 summarizes the formation constants for the binary bis- and mixed-ligand complexes of neodymium ion and the following important points for the formation of mixed complexes may be noticed from the tabulated data.

- The values of $\Delta \log K$ are negative, pointing to the preferential formation of ternary complexes than binary ones. However, in case of Nd^{III}-CMTSA-thiodipropionic acid system, $\Delta \log K$ is positive, which qualifies the positions of the equilibrium^{23,24} $MX + MY \rightleftharpoons MXY + M$. Despite of low $\Delta \log K$ (-0.14) in chlorosuccinic acid system, the sufficient stability of the mixed-ligand complex is due to the favourable value of K_{DXY} .
- Significantly greater values of K_{DXY} than 0.60 expected from statistical considerations except in succinic and itaconic acid systems, demonstrate the stabilized nature of mixed-ligand complexes.
- The values of $\log K_{MX}^{MX}$ and $\log K_{MY}^{MY}$ show the preferential formation of ternary complexes. A comparison of $\log K_{MY}^{MY}$ with $\log K_{MX}^{MX}$ values, especially in the systems involving methyl and ethyl substituted malonic acids, reveals the

TABLE 3—FORMATION CONSTANTS FOR TERNARY COMPLEXES OF NEODYMIUM(III)-CARBOXYMETHYLTHIOSUCCINIC (CMTSA)-DICARBOXYLIC ACIDS

Acids	Temp. 30°, $\mu = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO ₄)						$\Delta \log K$
	$\log K_{MXY}^M$	K_{DXY}	K_{MXY}^{MX}	K_{MY}^{MYX}	K_{MX}^M	$K_{MX_2}^{MX}$	
Succinic	6.76 (4)	0.13	2.64	3.40	3.38 ^a	—	-0.72
Itaconic	7.03 (3)	0.01	2.93	3.26	3.77 ^a	—	-0.84
Chlorosuccinic	6.38 (3)	0.71	2.28	3.96	2.42 (2)	—	-0.14
Methylmalonic	8.85 (2)	2.11	4.75	3.52	5.33 (2)	2.91 (1)	-0.58
Dimethylmalonic	8.58 (4)	2.18	4.48	3.63	4.95 (3)	2.68 (2)	-0.47
Ethylmalonic	8.56 (3)	1.83	4.46	3.46	5.10 (2)	2.84 (3)	-0.64
Diethylmalonic	8.61 (2)	2.01	4.51	3.49	5.12 (1)	2.71 (4)	-0.71
Thiodiacetic	7.08 (2)	0.61	2.98	3.86	3.22 ^b	—	-0.24
3,3'-thiodipropionic	7.77 (1)	1.31	3.67	4.56	3.21 ^b	—	+0.46

Standard deviations are given in parentheses.

^aRef. 9, ^bRef. 30.

preferential formation of mixed complexes than binary bis ones.

(d) The experimental data was utilized to plot the complex stability against the ligand basicity^{25,26}. A straight line relationship of positive slope was observed. Because of its double bond character, itaconic acid is deviated from the expected straight line, indicating the extra stabilization. As a part of systematic study of mixed-ligand complexes of Be²⁺, we discussed this interesting aspect of double bond character in maleic acid and explained on the basis of π electron distribution²⁷.

(e) It is clearly seen from the tabulated values of K_{MXY}^M and the stabilization parameters $\Delta \log K$ and K_{DXY} that the inductive effect of the substituent group has no great influence on the stability of these complexes, except in dimethylmalonic acid system. The presence of the two bulky substituents as in the case of Nd³⁺-CMTSA-diethylmalonic acid system seems especially to favour the formation of ternary species, probably by forcing the two carboxylate groups into the best position of chelation.

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